

**BRIGHT
SPACE**

Funded by
the European Union

Horizon Europe
Grant Agreement
No. 101060075

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

This is the 2nd newsletter of the BrightSpace project **WHERE YOU CAN:**

- Find out what BrightSpace is all about
- Read about the latest developments of the project
- Know more about networking with other EU projects
- Get information on upcoming events

What is BrightSpace ?

BrightSpace is an EC funded 5-year Horizon Europe research and innovation action aiming to design effective and sustainable strategies to navigate the EU agriculture within a Safe and Just Operating Space.

[Read more »](#) | [Read our project flyer](#)

Dear BrightSpace Community,

As we celebrate the first year of the BrightSpace project this November, it is with great excitement that we present to you the latest edition of our newsletter. This past year has been a testament to the dedication and collaborative spirit of our consortium to develop a shared vision for EU agriculture in a Safe and Just Operating Space.

One of the standout moments in 2023 was the 2nd annual consortium meeting hosted by the Czech University of Life Sciences in Prague (ČZU) on 12 and 13 October 2023, where we marked the project's first anniversary amidst spirited discussions and strategic planning. This gathering not only reinforced our commitment to BrightSpace's mission but also set the stage for the ambitious year ahead.

One of our significant accomplishments is the establishment of collaborations with several Horizon Europe projects, such as LAMASUS, GenBEcon, and RATION. This edition reflects on the exciting collaborations and joint initiatives that have emerged, including insights from the joint pre-congress workshops held at the EAAE 2023.

In a workshop organized by DG AGRI in Brussels, our project was introduced to European Commission officers as part of the Horizon-funded projects clustering on the topic of models and tools supporting agriculture policies. This exposure not only amplifies the visibility of BrightSpace but also positions us at the forefront of initiatives shaping the future of sustainable agriculture in Europe.

Building a robust stakeholder community is at the heart of our project, and we took a significant step in that direction with our first thematic seminar held on October 30th also included in this newsletter.

As you delve into this newsletter, we invite you to explore the latest developments, insights, and visions that have shaped the BrightSpace project throughout its first year. Your continued support and engagement have been instrumental in our journey so far, and we are excited about the milestones that await us in the year to come.

Thank you for being an integral part of the BrightSpace community.

Wishing you a peaceful festive season and all the best for the new year ahead.

Warm regards,

Marc Müller

BrightSpace Project Coordinator, on behalf of the BrightSpace coordination team

Latest news from BrightSpace

BRIGHT SPACE

Designing a Roadmap for Effective and Sustainable Strategies for Assessing and Addressing the Challenges of EU Agriculture to Navigate within a Safe and Just Operating Space

1st Thematic Seminar
Shaping the Safe and Just Operating Space: Thematic Areas, Domains and Indicators

30 October 2023
online

1st BrightSpace Thematic Seminar, 30 October 2023

36 experts from 13 EU countries, Ukraine and EC services (DG AGRI and DG ENV) participated at the 1st Thematic BrightSpace Seminar on 30 October 2023.

[Read more »](#)

Models and tools supporting agriculture policies
Clustering workshop of Horizon funded projects
EC DG AGRI, Brussels, 25 October 2023

agricore BESTMAP MIND STEP

BATModel better agricultural trade modelling for policy analysis

MATS

Trade 4 SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT

BRIGHT SPACE LAMASUS

BrightSpace Was Presented In An EC DG AGRI Workshop Of Horizon Funded Projects

BrightSpace was presented in a Brussels workshop of Horizon funded projects clustering in the topic of models and tools supporting agriculture policies, organized by EC DR AGRI.

[Read more »](#)

BRIGHT SPACE

2nd General Assembly
12-13 October 2023
Prague, Czech Republic

BrightSpace Annual Meeting

At the annual meeting partners reviewed the status quo of the project and the progress in the first year and drew up a road map for the second year of the project.

The online pdf version of the press release issued at our 2nd General Assembly is [available here](#).

eurostat

BRIGHT SPACE

WP2-WP3-WP7
received access to Eurostat microdata

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BrightSpace Consortium Was Granted Access to EUROSTAT Microdata

We are delighted to announce that four partners — Wageningen University & Research (WUR), the International Institute for Applied Systems Analysis (IIASA), the Thünen Institute, and the Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore (UCSC) — have successfully secured access to EUROSTAT microdata.

[Read more »](#)

Networking and Cooperation with Horizon Europe Projects

BrightSpace discussed at EAAE 2023 Pre-congress Workshop: Challenges for implementing the EU Farm-to-Fork Strategy – Pests, Plants and Profits

[Read more »](#)

BrightSpace discussed at EAAE 2023 Pre-congress Workshop: Towards new baseline scenarios in ex-ante modelling of landuse and -management

[Read more »](#)

Further highlights from our fellow projects

- LAMASUS Annual Consortium Meeting 28-29/11/2023, The Hague, NL [Read more »](#)
- LAMASUS presented at the MIND STEP project final event, 26/10/2023, Brussels, BE [Read more »](#)
- LAMASUS presented at the clustering workshop organized by DG AGRI, 25/10/2023, Brussels, BE [Read more »](#)

- MIND STEP Final Stakeholder Conference & partner meeting was held on 26/10/2023, Brussels, BE [Read more »](#)

Check out the MIND STEP project results:

- [MIND STEP Toolbox](#)
- [Scientific publications](#)
- [Public deliverables](#)

- 1st Responsible Research & Innovation (RRI) Workshop Online 09/11/2023 [Read more »](#)
- Science-Policy Symposium: New Genomic Techniques (NGTs) in Plants and Microalgae; 06/10/2023, Limassol, CY [Read more »](#)
- 2nd GeneBEcon Consortium Meeting; 04-05/10/2023, Limassol, CY [Read more »](#)

- 2nd Stakeholder forum workshop, online 13/10/2023 [Read more »](#)
- RATION Annual Meeting 27-29/09/2023, Larissa, GR [Read more »](#)
- RATION presented at XII European Congress of Entomology, 16-20/10/2023, Crete, GR [Read more »](#)

Watch our latest videos

BrightSpace Cooperates With The LAMASUS Horizon Europe Project Interview With Dr. Tamás Krisztin

LAMASUS is the sister project to BrightSpace. During the BrightSpace project kick off meeting, on 30 November 2022, we took an interview with Dr. Tamás Krisztin, senior research fellow of IIASA who is the scientific coordinator of the LAMASUS. Tamás gives insights into the details of both the BrightSpace and the LAMASUS projects, explains why interaction and coordination between the two projects is important, and speaks about the joint activities planned.

Follow us on Youtube: <https://www.youtube.com/@brightspace-horizon-eu-project>

Upcoming events

EU Agri-Food Days

Brussels, 5 - 8 December 2023
On-site event with web streaming #EUAgriFoodDays

Federal Ministry of Food and Agriculture

GLOBAL FORUM FOR FOOD AND AGRICULTURE

16th GFFA: Global Forum for Food and Agriculture
Food Systems for Our Future:
Joining Forces for a Zero Hunger World

🕒 17 - 20 January 2024
📍 Berlin, DE #GFFA

AES Agricultural Economics Society

ANNUAL CONFERENCE

🕒 18 - 20 March 2024
📍 Edinburgh, UK

32nd International Conference of Agricultural Economists

Transformation Towards Sustainable Agri-Food Systems

🕒 2-7 August 2024
📍 NEW DELHI, INDIA

ICAE 2024

Visit our website for more upcoming events: <https://brightspace-project.eu/events/>

**BRIGHT
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More information will be sent in our next BrightSpace newsletter scheduled for spring 2024.

Thank you for signing up to the [BrightSpace newsletters](#).

Further information can be found on the BrightSpace project homepage:

www.brightspace-project.eu | www.brightspace-horizon.eu

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